

MAIN DIFFICULTIES IN THE PROCESS OF SCIENTIFIC-TECHNICAL TEXT TRANSLATION

Gulimboyeva Nozima Azimboy qizi

TSUULL, senior student, Translation theory and practice faculty

e-mail: gulimboyevanozima@gmail.com

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Annotation. This article describes some of the problems encountered in the translation of scientific and technical terms that are currently relevant and their causes. In fact, not only students, but also experts face a number of difficulties when translating scientific and technical texts, because it is important to learn the terms of that particular field along with the set of general words in the translation.

Keywords: technical terms, translation problems, scientific and technical text, literature, difficulty, field, study, phrase, foreign language, vocabulary, concept.

A characteristic feature of scientific and technical literature is, on the one hand, clarity and brevity of expression, and on the other hand, strict logical sequence and completeness of presentation. Scientific and technical literature is characterized by the use of a large number of terms, as well as certain words and phrases. In this case, sentences are characterized by expansion, that is, the grouping of a large number of small clauses around the main clauses of the sentence, the presence of large determining groups and distributed homogeneous clauses, the wide use of introductory constructions, as well as the use of complex compounds and sentences. as applied. Acquiring the translation qualification is carried out differently depending on the level of preparation and characteristics of the person engaged in translation. For people who have good technical training, but do not know a foreign language well enough, first of all, problems in linguistic phenomena arise, that is, the main difficulties in understanding the meaning. This involves establishing semantic connections between individual words in a sentence, understanding language, structures, choosing the correct version of their translation, the ability to find a word in a dictionary, etc. How many words do you need to know to be able to read scientific and technical literature almost without using a dictionary? Special studies and experience in teaching translation show that a vocabulary of 2500-3000 words is enough for this. What words should be included in the minimum vocabulary first? Usually, the main feature of a scientific and technical text is the abundance of special terms in it. Maybe you should learn these terms first? Many people think so. To answer this question, we need to define what the terms mean. From a specialist's point of view, a term is a word that serves to define a specific concept.

Literature analysis and methodology

The number of terms for each field of science and technology is very large and is measured by tens of thousands. In addition, in connection with the development of science and technology, new special concepts and terms corresponding to them are constantly appearing. But at the same time, common words are often used as terms. It seems that in learning a foreign language, first of all, the main, the most important and it is necessary to master such terms that mean concepts. In addition, every specialist should also learn a number of the most important highly specialized terms in the field of related science and technology. To be able to determine the meaning of an unfamiliar word, you need to learn how to use the context, the meaning of the elements that make up the word, and other factors that affect the translation

of the word. There is a general context and a narrower context. General context refers to the content of a particular sentence and the whole text.

The general context serves as a background to reveal or clarify the meaning of each word. Narrow context means the lexical meaning of the words that are connected with the given word in the sentence and determine its meaning. It is possible to distinguish semantically connected words in a sentence. Therefore, to translate one of them, it is necessary to use a word that is far from it. The analysis of word formation is of great importance to translate an unfamiliar word in a text and to remember words. Therefore, it is necessary to know the ways of word formation and the basic elements of word formation, as well as to be able to translate complex words according to their components. This saves a person from the need to spend extra effort on memorizing a large number of derivative words, the meaning of which is easily deduced from the meaning of the main word. It is important to remember that most derived words are formed from verbs.

Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the acquisition of verbs. In the translation of scientific and technical literature, recognition of various grammatical forms and constructions in the text creates many difficulties related to translation. This applies primarily to constructions such as a group of nouns that have a common definition, when they do not recognize the "linking" of the article with descriptive words, which is the main feature of the common definition.

Conclusion

A particular difficulty is related to the translation of polysemantic grammatical forms and polysemantic auxiliaries. In this case, it is necessary to take into account several factors that help determine the grammatical function of the word and translate it into Uzbek. In the process of translation, the main focus is on the final goal - the most complete and correct understanding of the content of the text and the correct and correct expression of this content using the Uzbek language and focused on the expression of truth, actions can be performed freely, with minimal effort and time, as if by themselves, in other words, maximally automated.

Translation and interpreting is one of the oldest fields that have been forming in the culture of the peoples of the world for centuries. The peoples who have been living in different continents and regions of the earth for several thousand years have expressed their creative passions, interests, opportunities, and interests through means of translation. Through translation and interpreters, mankind became aware of each other and communicated with each other. Translation plays a huge and important role in human development and cultural life.

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